

Synthesis and spectroscopic studies of manganese (II) Iron (III) Cobalt (II), Nickel (II) and Copper (II) complexes with oxygen donor chalcone ligand

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Abstract

Selected first transition metals like Manganese (II) Iron (III) Cobalt (II), Nickel (II) and Copper (II) complexation with substituted Dehydroacetic acid Chalcone have been prepared and characterized by spectral and analytical techniques. ^1H NMR scans propose decent contribution of trans hydrogen in $\text{CH}=\text{CH}$ α β unsaturated moiety this is sign of chalcone formation. Electronic absorption spectral data's of metal coordination compounds moved towards lower or higher wavelength, which confirm the coordination of the Chelator to metal ion which shows the charge transfer band. The prepared Chalcone act as a bidentate ligand for the complexation reaction with Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II) and Fe(III) ions. Powder X-ray diffractograms studies of the coordination compounds shown that $[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_7)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and $[\text{Mn}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_7)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ are Hexagonal crystal arrangement, whereas Monoclinic crystal arrangement for $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_7)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_7)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_7)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ with P/2 type lattice.

Keywords: Dehydroacetic acid, metal complexes, chalcone

Introduction

There is rising curiosity in the pharmacological virtual of natural products is chalcones compose an essential sites of natural commodity. Chalcone are made up of open chain flavonoids it contains two aromatic or heteroaromatic moiety are fused by a three carbons having α β unsaturated carbonyl structure (Balaji H. Jawale, *et al.*, 2017; Patange, 2008) ^[1, 28]. The existence of a sensitive α , β unsaturated carbonyl moiety in chalcones is well known to be accountable for its antimicrobial effects (Prasad YR, *et al.*, 2008) ^[28]. In present times a number of chalcones have been investigated for its cytotoxic, insecticidal, antiviral, enzyme inhibitory, anticancer chemo preventive and mutagenic effects (Won SJ, *et al.*, 2005; Yu DC, *et al.*, 1982) ^[26, 27]. Numerous chalcones containing (-OH) hydroxy, (-OR) alkoxy functional sets in altered place have been stated to keep anti-infectious activity (Liu XL, *et al.*, 2008), antiulcer actions (Jeffrey JA, *et al.*, 1996) ^[6], antifungal properties (Lahtchev KL *et al.*, 2008) ^[8], antioxidant effects (Rao YK, *et al.*, 2009) ^[21], vasodilatory action (Ram VJ, *et al.*, 2000) ^[19], antimitotic activity (Khatib S, *et al.*, 2009) ^[7],

antimalarial propertis (Papo N, *et al.*, 2003) ^[14], antileishmanial action in addition to prohibition of organic peacekeepers relief, prohibition of leukotriene B₄, prohibition of tyrosinase and prohibition of aldose reductase effects (Balaji H. Jawale, *et al.*, 2017; Patange, 2008) ^[1, 28]. Gratitude of these results encouraged us to prepare novel chalcones as an active model for antimicrobial agents. On brief investigation of literature shown that no research work has been completed on some metal in first transition series with complexing materials of the 4-hydroxy-3-(3-(4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxyphenyl)acryloyl)-6-methyl-2H-pyran-2-one chalcone they are referred to Chelator derived from 4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxy benzaldehyde (syringaldehyde) and 3-acetyl-6-methyl-2H-pyran-2,4(3H)-dione (DHA). In this chapter, we are reveals the synthesis of novel chalcone, characterization carried out using modern tools. The transition metal [Cu (II), Ni (II), Co (II), Mn (II) and Fe (III)] complexes materials obtained from bidentate novel chalcone ligand having a carbonyl group openly connected to the α , β -unsaturated moiety derived from dehydroacetic acid and syringaldehyde.

Synthesis of the 4-hydroxy-3-(3-(4-hydroxy-3, 5-dimethoxyphenyl) acryloyl)-6-methyl-2h-pyran-2-one chelator

A chloroform solution having 0.01 mole of 3-acetyl-6-methyl-2H-pyran-2,4(3H)-dione (DHA), add few drops of piperidine base, then add alternately prepared solution 0.01 mole of 4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxy benzaldehyde (Syringaldehyde) in 20 ml chloroform, after this reaction mixture refluxed for 8-10 hours. After completion of reaction some of the chloroform-water azeotrope mixture

separated out by purification. Crude precipitate is appearing means product are formed they separated on sluggish vaporization of the enduring CHCl_3 . The subsequent crude precipitate was filtered, then washed with ethanol and recrystallized out with CHCl_3 solvent (Patange V.N, *et al.*, 2008; Munde A.S, *et al.*, 2009) [28, 12].

Reaction

Preparation of metal complexes with chelator

An accurately way out 0.2mole of Chelator chalcone in RBF having 30 ml of CHCl_3 solvent and Chelator liquefied absolutely. Simultaneously prepared solution of 0.01 mole of transition metal salt in 20 ml of dehydrated methanol was formerly added drop by drop to the solution of the Chelator. The reactants mixture were refluxed for 2 to 3 hours with constant stirring and then the mixture cooled to see the appearance of precipitate which infrequently initiate to the cold reaction combination, if precipitate not occurred then

10% methanolic solution of NH_3 was added drop by drop to rise the pH of reaction mixture till the metal chelate crude precipitates out absolutely. The crude precipitate was digested for half an hour. Finally solid metal chelate are obtained, they are separated out on slow evaporation then filtered it in hot form. It was washed through methanol and dried out in vacuum desiccator.

Reaction

Results and Discussion

I) Physical and Analytical Results

The elemental evaluates indications 1:2 (metal: ligand) stoichiometry for each of the chelates. The investigative statistics of the Chelator and their transition metal chelates matched well through the general empirical formula $[\text{M}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, where M =Iron(III), Manganese(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), $\text{L}=\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_7$. The chelates were diverse coloured, stable in normal condition, they are

insoluble in H_2O as well as common organic solvents but completely soluble in dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide (Balaji H. Jawale, *et al.*, 2017; Patange, 2008) [1, 28]. Meanwhile a sole crystal of the every chelates could not be isolated from any common organic solvent, the probable structure was anticipated founded on investigative, modern spectral, magnetic measurements also thermal records.

Table 1: Physicochemical records of Chelator and their transition metal complexes

Ligand/ Complexes	F.W.	M.P. (°C)	Yield %	Colour	Found (Caltd.), %			
					M	C	H	O
Ligand HL $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_7$	332	219	82	Yellow	-	61.22 (61.44)	4.76 (4.85)	33.70
$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{30}\text{FeO}_{14}$	718	300<	60	Golden	7.66 (7.77)	56.80 (56.84)	4.181 (4.21)	31.07 (31.18)
$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{30}\text{CuO}_{14}$	726	260	35	Celadon	8.72 (8.75)	56.21 (56.24)	4.11 (4.16)	30.71 (30.85)
$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{30}\text{CoO}_{14}$	721	272	70	Orange	8.09 (8.17)	56.55 (56.60)	4.10 (4.19)	30.97 (31.04)
$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{30}\text{MnO}_{14}$	717	300<	66	Brown	7.61 (7.66)	56.80 (56.91)	4.16 (4.21)	31.20 (31.22)
$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{30}\text{NiO}_{14}$	721	252	58	Green Yellow	8.09 (8.14)	56.60 (56.62)	4.17 (4.19)	30.95 (31.05)

II) ^1H NMR spectrum of chelator

The ^1H nuclear magnetic resonance spectrum of free Chelator in deuterated chloroform at normal temperature appearances the resulting signals. δ 2.72 (singlet, due to 3H for $-\text{CH}_3$ proton in dehydroacetic acid moiety), 3.97 (singlet, due to 6H, on 2 $-\text{OCH}_3$ proton of side chain aryl moiety), 5.97 (singlet, due to 1H, for C_5 -hydrogen of DHA moiety), 5.98 (singlet, due to 1H, on $-\text{OH}$ proton aryl ring), 7.28

(singlet, due to 2H, for side chain Ar-H adjacent methoxy group), 7.95 (doublet, due to 1H, β proton of α β unsaturated moiety on Chelator), 8.22 (doublet, due to 1H, α proton of α β unsaturated moiety on Chelator) and 18.17 (singlet, due to 1H, for phenolic $-\text{OH}$ proton of DHA moiety) (R.Gren, 1971; S.Forsen, *et al.*, 1960; V.Drevenkar, *et al.*, 1983)^[18, 23, 24].

Fig 1: ^1H NMR Spectrum of Chelator

Mass spectra of chelator

Mass spectral figures confirmed the structure of the newly synthesized Chelator as showed by the mother ion peaks

equivalent to its empirical mass, the mass spectrum of Chelator are given in following Fig.02.

Fig 2: Mass Spectrum of Chelator

Fourier transform infrared spectra of chelator and its chelates

The FTIR spectrum of free Chelator appearances specific

bands at 3390cm^{-1} for ν (OH) stretching of the aromatic side chain substituted moiety, 3100cm^{-1} ν (OH) of the intramolecular phenolic O-H stretching of the DHA moiety,

1716 cm^{-1} $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ stretching of lactone carbonyl in between DHA ring, 1639 cm^{-1} $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ stretching of α β unsaturated carbonyl group, 1248 cm^{-1} $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ stretching of phenolic in DHA moiety individually (Ramarao N., *et al.*, 1985; Carugo O., *et al.*, 1990; Balaji H. Jawale, *et al.*, 2017; Patange, 2008) [20, 3, 1, 28]. In the FTIR spectrum of each transition metal chelates, none of the any band was detected in the IR frequency area of 3200-3000 cm^{-1} . This indicates absence of $\nu(\text{OH})$ of the intramolecular phenolic O-H stretching of the DHA moiety at 3100 cm^{-1} proposes successive deprotonation of the phenolic functional group and chelation of phenolic oxygen to the transition metal ion. This was also sustained by an rising IR frequency in $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ stretching of phenolic in 3-acetyl-6-methyl-2H-pyran-2,4(3H)-dione (DHA) moiety (Rao P.V., *et al.*, 2003; Balaji H. Jawale, *et al.*, 2017; Patange, 2008) [22, 1, 28] by 15-45 cm^{-1} . The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ stretching of α β unsaturated carbonyl group was moved to lesser energy by respect to the free Chelator, signifying the

contribution of the α β unsaturated carbonyl group in the complexation (Ramarao N., *et al.*, 1985; Carugo O., *et al.*, 1990) [20, 3]. On the other hand a wide-ranging band representative of $\nu(\text{OH})$ of complexation water molecules was detected in between the IR frequency region 3570 and 3200 cm^{-1} . In case of Chelator and its transition metal complexes exhibited a conspicuous band in IR frequency at 1379 representative of $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C})$ linkage and 994 cm^{-1} *trans* $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ absorption in α β olephinic. The occurrence of different bands in the IR frequency region 600-450 cm^{-1} can be allotted to ν (Metal-Oxygen) vibration (Balaji H. Jawale, *et al.*, 2017; Patange, 2008; Nakamoto K., 1970) [1, 28, 13]. Therefore, the all above spectral data concluded that the Chelate chelated through the transition metal ions, they acts as mono deprotonated bi-dentate and the complexation happens through the α β unsaturated carbonyl oxygen and phenolic oxygen of 3-acetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-2H-pyran-2-one (enol form of DHA moiety).

Table 2: Specific IR frequencies of Chelator and its transition metal complexes

Ligand/ Complexes	ν (OH) (side chain phenyl moiety)	ν (OH) (dehydroacetic acid moiety)	ν (C=O) (lactone)	ν (C=O) (acetyl carbonyl)	ν (C-O) (phenolic)	ν (C=C) (trans)	ν (M-O)
Ligand HL C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₇	3390	3100(s)	1716(s)	1639(m)	1248(w)	994(s)	-
C ₃₄ H ₃₀ FeO ₁₄	3338	-	1701(m)	1643(w)	1204(s)	994(w)	541(s) 495(s)
C ₃₄ H ₃₀ CuO ₁₄	3370	-	1693(s)	1647(s)	1266(w)	965(w)	544(w) 448(s)
C ₃₄ H ₃₀ CoO ₁₄	3201	-	1690(s)	1643(s)	1246(s)	972(m)	552(s) 486(s)
C ₃₄ H ₃₀ MnO ₁₄	3387	-	1670(m)	1640(w)	1238(m)	1000(s)	579(m) 534(s)
C ₃₄ H ₃₀ NiO ₁₄	3358	-	1699(s)	1653(s)	1225(s)	999(s)	532(s) 519(s)

Fig 3: FTIR Spectrum of Chelator(L7)

Magnetic moment and UV analysis

The UV scans of Iron(III), Manganese(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) complexes were logged in dimethylformamide solvent. Three ${}^6\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{G})$, ${}^6\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{G})$ and ${}^6\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{E}_g(\text{G})$ types electronic transition occurred on the basis of ultraviolet spectrum at 14465 cm^{-1} , 21317 cm^{-1} and 24252 cm^{-1} of the Iron chelate respectively, proposing an octahedral confirmation of Iron(III), which was also definite by magnetic moment (5.92 μ_B) (Balaji H. Jawale, *et al.*, 2017; Patange, 2008; Lever A. B. P., 1968) [1,

28, 9]. The scans of the Copper(II) coordination compound involved of a wide-ranging band at 14219 cm^{-1} given to the ${}^2\text{E}_g \rightarrow {}^2\text{T}_{2g}$ electronic transition of a distorted octahedral configuration (Eichhorn G. L., *et al.*, 1953) [5]. Along with this transition, the band detected at 25327 cm^{-1} arises as of INCT (intra ligand charge transfer). The UV scans of the Cobalt (II) coordination compound displayed three electronic transition at 9478 cm^{-1} given to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$, 18649 cm^{-1} signifying to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})$ and finally 21549 cm^{-1} which are arises to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$,

correspondingly (Balaji H. Jawale, *et al.*, 2017; Patange, 2008) ^[1, 28], representing octahedral geometry nearby the Cobalt (II) ion. This geometry again confirmed by magnetic measurement of the Cobalt (II) coordination compound was 4.48 μ_B . The UV spectrum of the Manganese (II) coordination material obtained three electronic absorption at 18351 cm^{-1} are predictable to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, 19759 cm^{-1} are assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and lastly 23151 cm^{-1} , which signifying to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$, ${}^4E_{1g}(4G)$ bands individually (Balaji H. Jawale, *et al.*, 2017; Patange, 2008) ^[1, 28], showing an octahedral confirmation over the Manganese (II) coordination material. Finally we concluded the Manganese (II) coordination material are octahedral geometry on the basis of UV outcomes, supplementary definite by magnetic

measurement (5.72 μ_B). The electronic absorption scans of the Nickel(II) coordination compound showed three electronic transition ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, with respect to UV bands at 9350 cm^{-1} , 15700 cm^{-1} and 22469 cm^{-1} respectively. These electronic transition values, along with the magnetic measurement value (3.28 μ_B), suggesting an octahedral configuration of the Nickel (II) coordination compound (Lever A. B. P., 1968) ^[9]. The obtained values of ultraviolet scans and magnetic measurements conclude the stability of the complexes and tracks the order in terms of transition metal ions Cu(II)>Ni(II)>Co(II) (Balaji H. Jawale, *et al.*, 2017; Patange, 2008) ^[1, 28].

Table 3: Magnetic and Ultraviolet-visible spectral data of Chelator and its complexes.

Ligand/Complexes	μ_{eff}/μ_B	ν/cm^{-1}	Band assignment	Geometry
Ligand HL $C_{17}H_{16}O_7$	-	32442 40545	INCT ^a INCT	-
$C_{34}H_{30}FeO_{14}$	5.92	14465 21317 24252	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$ ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(G)$	Octahedral
$C_{34}H_{30}CuO_{14}$	1.98	14219 25327	${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ INCT	Distorted Octahedral
$C_{34}H_{30}CoO_{14}$	4.48	9478 18649 21549	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$	Octahedral
$C_{34}H_{30}MnO_{14}$	5.72	18351 19759 23151	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$ ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$, ${}^4E_{1g}(4G)$	Octahedral
$C_{34}H_{30}NiO_{14}$	3.28	9350 15700 22469	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$	Octahedral

XRD studies of chelator and their metal complexes

The Fe(III), Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(III) coordinated compound of Chelator were exposed to powder X-ray diffraction studies. The powder XRD data of individually the main peaks consuming comparative intensity more than 10% have been indexed through using Powder-X Computer

Software programming individually by trial and error technique (Carvajal J., *et al.*, 2004; Balaji H. Jawale, *et al.*, 2017; Patange, 2008) ^[4, 1, 28]. The Fe(III), Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(III) coordinated compound of Chelator their X-ray diffractograms, data and result are summarised in following Fig. 4 and Table 4.

Fig 4: X-ray Diffractogram of Iron (III) Chelator complex

CRYSTAL SYSTEM	: Hexagonal	90.000 90.000 60.000
LATTICE TYPE	: P 2/m	
RADIATION	: Cu	LATTICE PARAMETER
WAVELENGTH	: 1.540598 Å ⁰	a= 4.9168 α= 90
VOLUME	: 1672.81Å ³	b= 4.9168 β= 90
LAMBDA	: 1.54060 Å ⁰	c= 5.4089 γ=120
RECIP. LATTICE	: 0.08082 0.08082 0.10569	2Theta Start= 5 2Theta End= 70

Table 4: XRD data of Iron (III) Chelator complex

H	K	L	TH(OBS)	TH-ZERO	TH(CALC)	D(OBS)	D(CALC)	RI %
1	0	0	3.49407	3.50997	3.56908	12.58203	12.3739	87.2
0	0	1	4.64038	4.65627	4.6698	9.48903	9.4616	13.4
1	0	1	5.69498	5.71087	5.88235	7.74104	7.51613	28.6
1	1	0	6.38276	6.39865	6.18986	6.91189	7.14408	45.1
2	0	0	7.07054	7.08643	7.1521	6.24399	6.18695	28.1
0	0	2	9.409	9.42489	9.37099	4.70398	4.7308	6.2
1	0	2	9.95923	9.97512	10.03914	4.44693	4.41886	14.6
3	0	0	10.83042	10.84631	10.76351	4.09352	4.12463	12.9
1	1	2	11.38064	11.39654	11.26169	3.89831	3.94438	22.5
2	2	0	12.38939	12.40528	12.45348	3.5857	3.57204	17.6
2	1	2	13.30643	13.32233	13.39141	3.34289	3.32596	8.4
0	0	3	14.13177	14.14767	14.1369	3.15152	3.15387	8.2

The summarized data tells that the Fe(III) complex are Hexagonal system with P type lattice structure on basis of cell data and crystal lattice parameters.

Conclusion

¹HNMR scans propose decent contribution of trans hydrogen in CH=CH α β unsaturated moiety this is sign of chalcone formation. It was detected that in mass outcomes mother ion equivalent to the empirical mass of Chelator seem strong band at (333 m/e), this was a strong sign for the formation of the Chelator. The Chelator can form Ni(II), Cu(II), Mn(II), Co(II) and Fe(III) transition metal coordination compounds by the coordination number is six. FTIR spectrum, that the Chelator coordinated to metal ions over phenolic oxygen and α β unsaturated carbonyl oxygen atom and also coordinated water molecules. Powder X-ray diffractograms studies of the coordination compounds shown that [Fe(C₁₇H₁₆O₇)₂(H₂O)₂] and [Mn(C₁₇H₁₆O₇)₂(H₂O)₂] are Hexagonal crystal arrangement, whereas Monoclinic crystal arrangement for [Co(C₁₇H₁₆O₇)₂(H₂O)₂], [Ni(C₁₇H₁₆O₇)₂(H₂O)₂] and [Cu(C₁₇H₁₆O₇)₂(H₂O)₂] with P/2 type lattice.

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